

1 **Stimulation of the tractography-defined subthalamic nucleus regions correlates with**
2 **clinical outcomes**

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1 **Introduction**

2 Deep brain stimulation (DBS) of the motor subthalamic nucleus (mSTN) is a well-
3 established surgical treatment for patients with Parkinson's disease (PD). However, there is
4 still controversy about the optimal place to stimulate within the STN¹. Most authors state
5 that stimulation of the dorsolateral region of the STN is associated with better motor
6 results. This area would coincide with the mSTN, since it receives the projections from the
7 primary motor (M1) and supplementary motor areas (SMA), through the hyperdirect
8 pathway²⁻⁶. However, a strict functional segregation within the STN is debated because the
9 STN neurons have a very wide receptive field⁷, and a good effect on motor symptoms have
10 been achieved stimulating not only the dorsolateral STN⁸. On the other hand, it has been
11 suggested that stimulation of the more ventromedial areas of the STN or its surroundings is
12 the cause of cognitive and affective side effects. These STN areas have extensive
13 connections with associative and limbic areas⁹. In this work, we use computerize models of
14 the volume of activated tissue (VAT) to investigate whether the stimulation of
15 tractography-defined mSTN is correlated with motor improvement. Furthermore, we also
16 investigate whether the stimulation of the non-motor STN (nmSTN) or the current spread
17 outside of the STN is correlated with motor outcomes, affective, or neuropsychological
18 (NPS) effects.

19 **Materials and Methods**

20 *Patients*

21 We retrospectively analyzed 13 patients with idiopathic PD who underwent STN-DBS in
22 our center between 2012 and 2016, with at least one year of postoperative follow-up and
23 imaging data available for analysis. A movement disorder specialist evaluated all patients
24 and all of them met the criteria for surgical treatment. The disease severity was evaluated
25 before and after surgery by using the unified Parkinson's disease rating scale (UPDRS) part
26 III scoring in the OFF/ON medication state, and the daily amount of levodopa or other
27 dopaminergic medication was also recorded. All participants underwent a full NPS
28 evaluation before surgery and none of them suffered severe cognitive impairments that
29 would preclude surgery. The cognitive changes were evaluated with the following tests:

1 Trail Making test subtest A [TMT-A] performance time, Stroop Interference index,
2 Hopkins Memory Test (free recall score), total score of Mattis Dementia Rating Scale
3 [DRS-II], phonological [PVF] and categorical verbal fluencies [CVF], Judgment of Line
4 Orientation [JLO]¹⁰⁻¹². Furthermore, there was a set of affective symptoms evaluation,
5 which included Beck anxiety inventory (BDI-II), and the state-trait anxiety inventory
6 (STAI). The institutional board review approved the study and all patients provided written
7 consent for publication of the data.

8 *Data Acquisition and pre-processing*

9 All MRI studies were performed using a 3T clinical imager. The T1-weighted 3D Fast
10 SPGR IRprep sequence was acquired with the following parameters: repetition time (TR), 8
11 ms; echo time (TE), 2 ms; flip angle, 12; field of view (FOV), 240 mm; matrix, 256 × 256;
12 slices, 160; slice thickness, 1 mm; inversion time (TI) 450 ms; and isotropic voxels, 1 mm.
13 The FLAIR-FSE 3D sequence was acquired with the following parameters: TR, 6600 ms;
14 TE, 110 ms; TI, 2200 ms; FOV, 240 mm; matrix, 256 × 256; slices, 160; and slice
15 thickness, 1 mm. These parameters enabled reconstruction with a 1-mm isotropic voxel
16 size. Diffusion weighting (DWI) was encoded along 55 independent orientations using a
17 single-shot multi-slice 2D spin-echo diffusion-sensitized and fat-suppressed echo planar
18 imaging (EPI) sequence, with b-values of 0-1000 mm²/s, TR/TE of 9600/82 ms, FOV of
19 250 × 250 mm, matrix of 96 × 96, and slice thickness of 2.6 mm with no inter-slice gap,
20 resulting in isotropic voxels of 2.6 mm. Post-operative computed tomography (CT) scan
21 was acquired on a multislice Philips ® Brilliance 64 with spiral pitch of 0.891, rotation of
22 0.75 s, no gantry tilt, matrix of 512 × 512, slice thickness of 1 mm; tube voltage of 120 kV,
23 and tube current of 75 mA. All structural and diffusion image data were preprocessed using
24 tools from FSL [Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the Brain [FMRIB] Software
25 Library (FSL), <http://www.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl>]. DWI, FLAIR 3D and T1 data underwent
26 skull stripping using BET toolbox (FSL)¹³. For DWI data, Eddy current-induced distortion
27 and movement correction (Eddy toolbox, FSL) were applied¹⁴. Using BEDPOSTX,
28 estimates of fiber orientation and their uncertainty were calculated at each voxel with the
29 default parameters and local DTI fitting (DTIFIT, FDT toolbox, FSL) was also performed

1 ¹⁵. Both the structural and diffusion images were linearly coregistered and non-linearly
2 registered to standard space using FSL FLIRT and FNIRT with default parameters ¹⁶.

3 *DBS surgery, follow up and programming*

4 The surgical procedure was performed based on the coordinates of the STN given by the
5 Schaltenbrand–Wahren atlas ¹⁷, and adjustment of the target was based on the direct
6 identification of the STN on the preoperative MRI. Finally the target was confirmed with
7 intraoperative recordings and clinical evaluation as detailed elsewhere ^{18,19}. Seven patients
8 were implanted with a DBS lead model 3389 (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN) and six with
9 the 8-contact DBS lead (Boston Scientific, Valencia, CA). After surgery, a CT scan was
10 performed and the images were fused with the preoperative MRI. Three weeks after surgery
11 the patients were evaluated by a movement disorders specialist to determine the optimal
12 stimulation settings that was based on the clinical benefit and tolerability while defining the
13 thresholds for side effects. The patients were regularly evaluated with a follow-up visit
14 every two or six months, the UPDRS III scores and changes in dopaminergic medication
15 were recorded in each visit. Between six months and one year after surgery, the same NPS
16 test battery and affective evaluation were tested in the patients ²⁰, and complete records of
17 these tests were available for 10 out of 13 patients.

18 *Deterministic tractography analysis*

19 Deterministic tractography (DT) was performed in the StealthViz software package
20 (Medtronic Iberica) with the following parameters: 0,33 fractional anisotropy start,
21 maximal angle 45°, and fiber length of 1. The delineation of the mSTN was previously
22 published by our group and the aim of this method is to obtain anatomical regions within
23 the STN based on the density of fibers passing through the MRI-defined STN ^{18,21}. Shortly,
24 we segmented three anatomical regions in 3D FLAIR space: the STN, the precentral gyrus,
25 and the posterior part of the superior frontal gyrus (henceforth referred to as M1 and SMA
26 respectively). After the segmentation, we performed the fiber tracking from the M1 and the
27 SMA. Then, we performed a multiplanar voxelized reconstruction of each tract and we
28 selected the voxels in the intersection between each tract (M1 or SMA) and the STN.
29 Finally, we created four segments of the STN based on the intersection with the tracts: 1)

1 m1STN, 2) smaSTN, 3) the addition of both motor areas (m1STN and smaSTN) was
2 defined as the mSTN, 4) and the rest of the STN was defined as the nmSTN (Fig 1).

3 *Generation, modelling and registration of the volume of activated tissue*

4 At the time of the analysis, the GUIDE™ software package (Boston Scientific , Valencia,
5 CA) was used to generate the DBS models of all patients based on the clinically optimal
6 stimulation settings ²². Patients with lead model 3389 (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN) were
7 evaluated with the same software as the distance and the lengths of the contacts is the same
8 as the 8-contacts DBS lead. The measurements of the graphical representation of the VAT
9 were then extracted from the software to do a 3D reconstruction of the models at the MRI
10 resolution (1 mm) using autodesk®, materialise mimics®, and StealthViz software
11 packages. In most patients, the VAT was spherical and we calculated the volume (mm³) by
12 obtaining the radius of the sphere. The measurements of the non-spherical models were
13 obtained based on an approximation of the models to several geometrical shapes such as
14 spherical caps, cylinders and oval shapes (Fig 1). The VAT models were then coregistered
15 with the CT scan by aligning the model with the center point of the best clinical contact
16 (monopolar) or the midpoint between the center of both contacts (bipolar) based on the
17 specifications of the lead model. This process allowed automatic VAT coregistration with
18 the preoperative MRI (Fig 1).

19 *Statistical and overlap analysis*

20 The overlap coefficients (OCs) between the VAT models and the STN segments of each
21 patient were computed using the Fiji open-source image software package with the
22 JACoP™ plugin ²³. The Mander's overlap coefficient (OC) was used ^{24,25}. Four OCs were
23 calculated for all patients by side (left or right): $VAT \cap m1STN$, $VAT \cap smaSTN$,
24 $VAT \cap mSTN$, $VAT \cap nmSTN$ and these coefficients were then normalized to be compared
25 across patients. Also, we measured the VAT outside of the STN (VATout) using *fslstats*.
26 On the other hand, we computed the percentage of motor improvement based on the pre
27 and postoperative UPDRS III scores in all patients. Moreover, the degree of reduction of
28 the levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD) was also calculated as a percentage based on
29 pre and postoperative standardize doses of the dopaminergic medication ²⁶. Using items 20-

1 26 of the UPDRS III score, we calculate the degree of lateralized motor improvement
2 (LatUPDRS) per side of the patients (25 scores, one patient had unilateral therapy), and the
3 improvement of the lateralized subscores (LatSS) (bradykinesia, rigidity, or tremor). The
4 percentage of change in NPS and affective scores at post-DBS respect to baseline
5 assessments and the number of days between assessments were calculated. The paired
6 Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to assess the pre and postoperative difference in motor,
7 NPS, affective scores, and LEDD reduction. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient
8 was used to analyze the correlation between the OCs, or the VATout with the degree of
9 motor improvement (Lat UPDRS, each Lat SS), reduction of LEDD, changes in NPS scores
10 (OCs were averaged between sides), and changes in affective evaluation. The statistical
11 analysis was performed using the GraphPad prism software package (California, USA), and
12 $p < .05$ was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

13 *Probabilistic tractography analysis*

14 Whole-brain probabilistic tractography (PT) was generated from individually defined STN
15 masks (m1STN, smaSTN, nmSTN) and the VATout mask in seven patients of this cohort.
16 Five thousand random samples per voxel, exclusion mask using the inverse T1 skull-
17 stripped mask, and other default parameters were used. These maps were normalized by
18 dividing the individual tract by the total number of streamlines sent out (waytotal number)
19 and thresholded at 95% of the total streamlines²⁷. The resulting connectivity distributions
20 from each patient were warped into standard space to create an averaged common
21 population connectivity map for each mask (m1STN, smaSTN, nmSTN, VATout). These
22 population maps were then smoothed using a 0.5 mm Gaussian kernel and thresholded at
23 75% of the robust mean for illustration purposes.

24 **Results**

25 There were 13 patients (2 females and 11 males), with a mean age of 62 years, mean
26 disease duration of 16.3 years and a mean follow up period of 25 months. The motor scores
27 (UPDRS III) showed a statistically significant improvement after STN-DBS ($Z = -3.1798$,
28 $p < .001$; $Z = -3.1798$, $p < .001$ respectively). On the other hand, NPS results indicated that
29 scores were significantly better at baseline than under DBS therapy in visuospatial

1 functions (JLO test), categorical verbal fluency (CVF) and sustained attention (TMT-A)
2 ($Z=-2.572$, $p<.010$; $Z=-2.609$, $p<.009$; $Z=-1.993$, $p<.046$, respectively). There were no
3 further significant differences neither in NPS nor affective test scores ($p=n.s.$) (Table 1).

4 *Motor, neuropsychological and affective outcomes*

5 We found a significant positive correlation between the $VAT \cap mSTN$ and the improvement
6 in contralateral LatUPDRS ($r=.55$, $p<.004$). Moreover, we found that the
7 $VAT \cap mSTN$
8 was significantly correlated with the contralateral improvement of bradykinesia ($r=.55$,
9 $p<.004$). Furthermore, the $VAT \cap smaSTN$ showed significant correlation with the
10 contralateral LatUPDRS ($r=.41$, $p<.04$) and the bradykinesia ($r=.41$, $p<.04$) but not with
11 rigidity or tremor. Finally, we found a negative correlation between $VAT \cap nmSTN$ and the
12 contralateral improvement of rigidity ($r=-.59$, $p<.002$). No other correlation was found
13 between the $VAT \cap m1STN$ and any of the motor outcomes or LEDD reduction. We found
14 a median volume of the VAT per side of 113.1 mm^3 and a volume of VAT outside of the
15 STN of 64.6 mm^3 . However, no significant correlation was found between the VAT_{out}
16 (mm^3) and any of the motor scores or the LEDD reduction (Fig 2). Neuropsychological
17 results indicated that there was a significant positive correlation between $VAT \cap nmSTN$
18 and interference measured by Stroop test ($r=.72$, $p<.02$). Regarding the stimulation outside
19 the STN, there was a significant positive correlation between VAT_{out} and the degree of
20 change in visuospatial functions (based on JLO test) ($r=.93$, $p<.00$), and categorical verbal
21 fluency (CVF) ($r=.86$, $p<.00$). In relation with affective functions, there was significant
22 correlation between increase in depression score (measured by BDI) and right VAT_{out}
23 ($r=.70$, $p<.03$), and between bilateral VAT_{out} and increase STAI-Stait score ($r=.72$, $p<.03$)
24 (Fig 3). No further correlations were found statistically significant.

25 *Probabilistic tractography*

26 The connectivity distribution maps from the $m1STN$ showed connections mainly with the
27 ipsilateral M1 and the cerebellothalamocortical system (CTCS). The tractography maps
28 from the $smaSTN$ showed a similar pattern of connectivity as the $m1STN$ but with more
29 significant connections with the SMA and the CTCS. These findings replicate the
30 connectivity pattern obtained by the deterministic approach to delineate the STN segments.

1 Finally, we used the nmSTN as seed region and we found significant connections with the
2 limbic and associative circuits: dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC), orbitofrontal
3 cortex, ventromedial prefrontal cortex. Also, we found connections of the nmSTN with the
4 CTCS, the posterior temporal region and the posterosuperior part of the insula (Fig 4). The
5 VATout showed strong connectivity with the prefrontal and motor regions. The CTCS was
6 also significantly connected with the stimulated regions outside of the STN. Bilateral
7 projections to the insular and left parietotemporal regions were also found (Fig 5).

8 **Discussion**

9 We have found that the stimulation of the tractography-delineated mSTN positively
10 correlated with improvement of contralateral motor function, and contralateral
11 bradykinesia. However, between the primary and secondary motor areas, only the
12 stimulation of the smaSTN was significantly correlated with the improvement in
13 contralateral motor function and bradykinesia. Also, there was a negative correlation
14 between the stimulation of the nmSTN with the contralateral improvement of rigidity. On
15 the other hand, it seems to be a mild cognitive decline in PD patients after the surgery in
16 visuospatial and semantic memory scores, and the maintenance of these functions within
17 the normal range is correlated with the stimulation outside of the STN. Conversely,
18 impairment in attention is correlated with stimulation of the nmSTN, while impairments in
19 perceived depression or anxiety is correlated with the stimulation outside of the STN.

20 There is evidence that the specific sweet spot for STN-DBS in PD is the motor area of the
21 STN, which is located at its dorsolateral zone^{3,21,28-31}. However, other authors have found
22 the most clinically effective electrodes anterior-medially located with respect to the
23 sensorimotor STN, so-called ‘central STN’^{8,32}. Moreover, the modulation of the premotor
24 circuit instead of the motor circuit has been related with clinical benefit in PD³³⁻³⁵, and
25 recent evidence showed a positive correlation between clinical benefit and SMA/VAT
26 connectivity³⁴. This is in line with experimental evidence which states that secondary
27 motor areas directly influence lower brain centers as a compensatory mechanism of
28 dopamine depletion, which underscores the importance of the premotor circuit in the PD
29 pathophysiology³⁶. In this work, we found the smaSTN located ventromedial with respect
30 of the m1STN and the stimulation of the smaSTN, but not the m1STN, was significantly

1 correlated with the improvement of contralateral motor function and bradykinesia.
2 Anatomically, the central region of the STN, has been described as an overlap region
3 between the premotor and associative circuits through the SMA and DLPFC afferents ^{4,37,38}.
4 Taken together these findings could suggest a preferential involvement of the premotor
5 circuit over the motor circuit at least in some of the beneficial effects of DBS in PD patients
6 such as bradykinesia ^{39,40}. However, in our series the majority of patients were
7 predominantly rigid-akinetic. Thus, with our results we could not rule out the contribution
8 of the projections from the M1 to the STN in the motor outcomes, especially tremor, whose
9 control is known to be obtained by electrical stimulation of M1 ⁴¹. Interestingly, we found
10 an negative relationship between the VAT∩nmSTN and improvement in rigidity. Perhaps
11 this is due to the fact that nmSTN was not damaged in our patients (since patients with
12 dementia or other NPS deficits were excluded). We hypothesize that an active nmSTN
13 helps improvement in rigidity when the mSTN is blocked, since it would inhibit non-
14 desired movements. When blocked by a greater VAT∩nmSTN overlap, improvement in
15 rigidity would less happen.

16 One of the main theories of the beneficial effect of STN-DBS is the disruption of abnormal
17 signals through the modulation of the hyperdirect pathway ⁴²⁻⁴⁵. Conversely, other evidence
18 suggests a preferential suppression of the indirect pathway in the therapeutic effects of
19 STN-DBS ⁴⁶, and this is probably related with the down-regulation of the hyperdirect
20 pathway in the dopamine-depleted state ⁴⁷. Also, one of the key connections of the indirect
21 pathway, the pallidosubthalamic fibers, arrive at the dorsolateral regions of the STN,
22 probably in close spatial relationship with the hyperdirect pathway ^{48,49}. Therefore, the
23 specific brain networks influenced by STN-DBS have yet to be elucidated since the
24 pallidosubthalamic, subthalamopallidal, pallidothalamic, corticosubthalamic, and
25 nigrofugal pathways, among others converge in a region closely related with the
26 dorsolateral STN ⁵⁰. On the other hand, there is still controversy about whether stimulation
27 of the nucleus or the white matter afferents is the optimal target ^{6,44,45,51}. In patients with
28 PD, the stimulation of axonal tissue near the dorsal border of the STN has been correlated
29 with a greater motor improvement ⁵². However, other authors claimed that stimulation
30 inside the MR-defined STN is more clinically optimal compared with stimulation outside
31 the STN ^{32,53-55}. Furthermore, slightly different locations around the subthalamic area are

1 related with specific clinical effects such as the best clinical benefit of rigidity, bradykinesia
2 and absence/presence of paresthesias ⁵⁶. These dissociative effects are supported by the
3 finding that different points within the STN region could have different physiological
4 mechanisms to improve bradykinesia ⁵⁷. Surprisingly, we found a median of 50% of the
5 VAT was outside of the STN, therefore a number of highly eloquent anatomical structures
6 such as prelemniscal radiations, zona incerta, lenticular fascicle, among others, could be
7 modulated at the same time, which in fact has demonstrated correlation with clinical
8 outcome ⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. These findings support the need for more imaging and clinical correlated
9 studies to render the STN region to a target map area for individualized therapy. The impact
10 of directional leads on clinical improvement and side effects could bring light in this matter
11 in the near future.

12 It is suggested that there is an initial worsening in executive function after DBS surgery
13 such as memory and verbal fluency, but these deficits tend to return to baseline after 3-12
14 months after surgery ⁶¹⁻⁶³. Moreover, previous studies demonstrate detrimental effect of
15 STN-DBS on visuospatial and categorical verbal functions ⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. According to our results it
16 seems that as stimulation increases outside of the STN the scores in categorical verbal
17 fluency and visuospatial function are closer to normal. In support of that finding, it has
18 been previously proposed that the extra-stimulation coming from adjacent STN areas may
19 tend to normalize such functions by enhancing connectivity in the memory networks ⁶⁷.
20 Furthermore, some studies support the improvement of switching functions under STN
21 DBS ^{68,69} but there are no literature regarding the different effects of nmSTN vs mSTN
22 stimulation on these functions. As shown in our tractographical results, nmSTN is
23 connected to the conflict resolution areas ⁷⁰. The high-frequency stimulation of the nmSTN
24 may be triggering a cognitive imbalance and so, causing detrimental performance in
25 attention tasks ⁷¹. Some authors reported no change or mild improvement on depression and
26 anxiety in patients with STN-DBS ^{32,53,72}, probably related with the improvement of the
27 quality of life of the patients, which has been clearly demonstrated with STN-DBS.
28 However, other evidence demonstrate that depression is worse with STN-DBS than with
29 pallidal stimulation ⁷³ probably related with the postoperative reduction of dopaminergic
30 medication. In our work, stimulation outside of the STN is correlated with increased
31 anxiety and depression (right side) in line with other evidence ⁷⁴. However, other authors

1 have found that STN-DBS reduces anxiety scores in a long term follow-up ^{75,76}. These
2 differences may demonstrate the previously explained idea of the cognitive imbalance, and
3 how the accumulative effect of medication and stimulation may increase affective and
4 cognitive symptoms. Therefore, imaging analysis alone would not completely explain these
5 complex changes in behavior and cognition after STN DBS. Further studies should
6 differentiate between associative and limbic segments of the STN and correlate VAT
7 overlap with cognitive and limbic measures.

8 Tractography has not been widely used to prospectively target the STN in DBS surgery
9 because of reproducibility issues, coregistration errors, data acquisition issues, and complex
10 methodology. However, tractography has been adequately validated using
11 electrophysiological studies to be used as an adjunct in DBS or lesioning surgery ⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰.
12 Moreover, some DBS targets have been successfully identified using this technology ^{27,81}.
13 The non-segregated nature of the STN makes it difficult to sharply divide the nucleus in
14 functional territories as it has been described in tracing studies, due to the overlap between
15 the different circuits, whose limits would probably vary among different individuals ⁹. In
16 this study, we delineated these regions based on fiber density and we used those regions as
17 an approximation of the STN areas receiving motor or premotor input. Moreover, the group
18 probabilistic maps showed reproducibility of the seed regions used in the the deterministic
19 approach (Fig 4). The retrospective nature of the analysis, the lack of the analysis of the
20 motor side effects and the small number of observations are the main limitations of this
21 work. Also, the use of two different DBS electrode montages would affect our assumptions
22 on the VAT modelling. Regarding NPS evaluation, among the limitations some test could
23 not be included in the analysis because of the data missing in more than one participant,
24 some of the test are not adequately adapted for PD patients (i.e. MMSE) and further studies
25 should try to focus on those functions already described as linked with STN-DBS in PD
26 instead of general dementia scales (i.e. MDRS).

27 In the near future, patient-specific connectivity analysis could give us the opportunity to
28 tailor targeted approaches to treat such complex diseases such as movements or psychiatric
29 disorders. However, all the current methodologies to individualize DBS targets are plagued
30 of technical limitations and cumbersome pipelines ^{3,18,28,31}. Finally, despite being only a

1 gross estimate of the voltage spread of the DBS electrode, the VAT models have
2 demonstrated to be accurate, and in some situations, outperform the clinical guide of DBS
3 programming^{22,52}. These models provide an anatomical visual feedback in a wide range of
4 stimulation settings and contact selection, which is useful in making clinically relevant
5 predictions but it depends on the accurate position of the electrode^{22,51,82,83}. In this sense, to
6 achieve the best possible clinical outcome and minimum side effects it is necessary to begin
7 with the best possible defined trajectory, which would be based on the individualized
8 target¹. Prospective studies will be needed to validate methods for individualized target
9 localization prior surgery, as avoiding certain STN areas seem instrumental for a more
10 efficient programming session, which might not be completely compensated even with
11 current steering technology. These studies should be complemented with an unbiased and
12 straightforward methodology applicable in the clinical setting. Ideally, advance imaging
13 and programming methods should provide the ability to focus stimulation in the STN region
14 related with maximal improvement of specific symptoms and to avoid areas associated with
15 cognitive or affective adverse effects.

16 **Conclusion**

17 Our results suggested that stimulation of the tractography-delineated motor STN, mainly
18 smaSTN, is correlated with a greater motor improvement and bradykinesia improvement.
19 Furthermore, the stimulation of the non-motor STN is correlated with impaired attention
20 and a negative effect in the improvement of rigidity. The impairment in affective symptoms
21 may be related with stimulation outside of the STN.

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1 **Tables and figures**

2 **Figure 1:** Description of the study. A, The mSTN was delineated based on the projections
3 from M1 and SMA. This region was later divided in smaSTN (fibers from SMA) and
4 m1STN (fibers from M1). B, The shape and measurements of the VAT models were
5 obtained from the GUIDE® software. These models were voxelized at the structural MRI
6 resolution (1 mm). The VATs were then coregistered with the CT scan and aligned to the
7 contact configuration of the electrode. This allowed automatic registration with structural
8 MRI and the STN segments to calculate the overlap.

9 **Figure 2:** Motor outcomes: A, B, The contralateral UPDRS and bradykinesia improvement
10 showed a positive correlation with the $VAT \cap smaSTN$. C, The contralateral rigidity
11 improvement showed a negative correlation with the $VAT \cap nmSTN$. D, This patient had
12 differential clinical improvement on both sides showing better improvement in
13 bradykinesia on the right (88%) compared with the left side (58%). The VAT model (red)
14 on the left overlapped more with motor STN segments (green) than the VAT model on the
15 right. s, superior; i, inferior; r, right; l, left, HP, hyperdirect pathway.

16 **Figure 3:** Neuropsychological and affective outcomes: A. Statistically significant
17 correlation between % of change in Stroop test and VAT intersection. The graph displays
18 that the higher the overlap between VAT and non-motor STN, the higher the worsening in
19 attention interference (measured by Stroop test). B. Statistically significant correlation
20 between % of change in Judgement in Line Orientation (JLO) test and the VATout. The
21 graph presents that the larger the VAT out of the STN, the higher the improvement in
22 visuospatial abilities (measured by JLO test). C. Statistically significant correlation between
23 % of change in Categorical Verbal Fluency (CVF) and the VATout. The graph indicates
24 that the larger the VAT out of the STN, the higher the improvement in semantic fluency
25 tasks (measured by CVF test). D. Statistically significant correlation between % of change
26 in Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) and the VAT. The graph shows that the larger the
27 VATout on the right side, the larger the impairment in depression symptoms (measured by
28 BDI). E. Statistically significant correlation between % of change in State-Trait Anxiety
29 Inventory (STAI) and the VATout. The graph represents that the larger the VAT out of the

1 STN, the larger the impairment in anxiety symptoms (measured by subscale STAIstate
2 from STAI).

3 **Figure 4:** Group probabilistic tractography maps of the STN segments demonstrate
4 corticosubthalamic projections (hyperdirect pathway). A, The m1STN was used as seed
5 region demonstrating common direct pathways to the M1 and weak connectivity with the
6 cerebellar nuclei. B, The smaSTN showed strong connectivity with the cerebellar nuclei
7 and the SMA. C, The nmSTN shows strong connectivity with the DLPFC, OFC, vmPFC,
8 cerebellar nuclei, and posterior temporal region. D, 3D rendering of the tractography maps
9 illustrates the connectivity of the 3 STN segments (same color code). E, 3D rendering of
10 the STN segments of a representative patient (same color code).

11 **Figure 5:** Group probabilistic tractography maps of the VAT outside of the STN. The
12 VATout mask was used as a seed region showing strong connectivity with the CTCS,
13 prefrontal region, motor cortices and temporoinsular region. Furthermore, weaker
14 connectivity with the left parietal region was also shown. This pattern of connectivity
15 demonstrates the widespread effects of DBS on brain networks. A, Axial views B, Sagittal
16 views. C, All VATs (red) summed, and the STN with the motor regions (green, smaSTN;
17 yellow, m1STN)

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21

Fiber tracking from M1, SMA

STN segments

Overlap analysis

VAT models

Voxelized models

CT reg

Patients

A

B

C

Clinical parameter	Baseline. Median (IQR)	Post-DBS. Median (IQR)	p value	% reduction Mean (SD)
LEDD	1302 (1075-1819)	620 (400-985)	.000	48.2 (26.7)
Motor				% improvement Mean (SD)
UPDRS III	37 (22-49)	13 (10-24.5)	.001	46.8 (22.3)
Bradykinesia	8 (5.5-10.5)	5 (2.5-6)	.000	39.6 (34.1)
Rigidity	4 (3-5)	1 (1-2)	.000	62.7 (25.9)
Tremor	0 (0-3.5)	0 (0-0)	.003	41.1 (48.7)
NPS				% worsening Mean (SD)
JLO	26.5 (22.8-29)	23 (17.8-26.3)	.011	14.2 (11.5)
CVF	18.5 (16.5-30.5)	17 (11.8-21.8)	.010	20.5 (16.6)
TMT_A	50.5 (30.8-75.3)	58 (36-104)	.046	49.9 (98.5)

Table 1: Summary of the clinical outcomes of our patients. LEDD, levodopa equivalent daily dose. JLO, Judgement in Line Orientation. CVF, Categorical Verbal Fluency. TMT_A, trail making test subtest A. IQR, interquartile range. SD, standard deviation.